

A decade of domoic acid in Monterey Bay -SPATT observations give new insight on toxin variability

Aubrey Trapp*, Kendra Hayashi, Raphael M. Kudela

Department of Ocean Sciences, University of California Santa Cruz, Santa Cruz, U.S.A.

**corresponding author's email: ajtrapp@ucsc.edu*

Abstract

The risk of amnesic shellfish poisoning from *Pseudo-nitzschia* sp. blooms and subsequent domoic acid events has persisted in Monterey Bay on the central California coast for nearly three decades. Over this time, HAB monitoring has experienced rapid advancement in methods and technologies designed to predict toxic blooms and mitigate losses. One such innovation, solid phase adsorption toxin tracking (SPATT), is now widely applied for passive sampling of dissolved toxins, often complementing toxin quantification from shellfish and direct measurements from seawater. Here we show 10 years (2010 - 2020) of domoic acid measured by SPATT in Monterey Bay and investigate trends in relation to key environmental factors. Of the three SPATT resins deployed (HP-20, SP-207, and SP-700) results indicate subtle differences that may affect how well domoic acid from SPATT resembles toxin accumulation in shellfish. In recent years, SPATT samples contained higher levels of domoic acid than might be expected by direct analysis of seawater and extractions from mussels. Analysis of monitoring data from the Santa Cruz Wharf repository revealed complex relationships between passive sampling, cell counts, and direct analysis from seawater, though there was a negative correlation between all toxin parameters and nutrient concentrations. To our knowledge, this is the longest dataset for detecting domoic acid by SPATT. Continued analysis may give insight on future trends and greater understanding of the environmental drivers of dissolved marine biotoxins in Monterey Bay.

Keywords: SPATT, domoic acid, dissolved toxins, harmful algae monitoring

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7035160>

Introduction

Monterey Bay, on the central California coast, hosts high productivity and biodiversity. Since 2009, observations from solid phase adsorption toxin tracking (SPATT) have supplemented direct monitoring of domoic acid (DA) at the Santa Cruz Wharf (SCW). The present study revisits an approximately weekly SPATT sampling effort first presented in Lane *et al.* (2010) a neurotoxin produced by some species of the diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia*, can remain undetected in sentinel shellfish stocks during toxic blooms and subsequent marine bird and mammal mass mortality events. Solid Phase Adsorption Toxin Tracking (SPATT) and evaluates relationships between domoic acid observations and key environmental factors. SPATT developed as a passive sampling method for monitoring algal biotoxins and is now widely deployed to monitor a suite of marine and freshwater toxins (MacKenzie *et al.*, 2004; MacKenzie, 2010; Roué *et al.*, 2018) including the low polarity lipophilic compounds such as the pectenotoxins and the okadaic acid complex toxins, are dissolved in the seawater. The results of field trials during *Dinophysis acuminata* and *Protoceratium reticulatum* blooms are presented. These data prove the concept and demonstrate that the technique provides a means of forecasting shellfish contamination events and predicting the net accumulation of polyether toxins by mussels. As an early warning method it has many advantages over current monitoring techniques such as shellfish-flesh testing and phytoplankton monitoring. In contrast to the circumstantial evidence provided by genetic probe technologies and conventional phytoplankton monitoring methods, it directly targets the toxic compounds of interest. The

extracts that are obtained for analysis lack many of the extraneous lipophilic materials in crude shellfish extracts so that many of the matrix problems associated with chemical and biological analysis of these extracts are eliminated. Analyses can confidently target parent compounds only, because analytical and toxicological uncertainties associated with the multiplicity of toxin analogues produced by *in vivo* biotransformation in shellfish tissues are reduced. Time integrated sampling provides a good simulation of biotoxin accumulation in filter feeders and the high sensitivity provides lengthy early warning and conservative estimates of contamination potential. The technique may reduce monitoring costs and provide improved spatial and temporal sampling opportunities. When coupled with appropriate analytical techniques (e.g. LC-MS/MS multi-toxin screens, ELISA assays, receptor binding assays). While passive sampling by SPATT has several advantages over other HAB monitoring methods, including avoiding complications from cell counts and shellfish extractions, its effectiveness for predicting future toxin events in shellfish has shown mixed results (Roué *et al.*, 2018). Here we use a long-term dataset with strong spatial and temporal resolution to compare SPATT observations with direct analysis of domoic acid and *Pseudo-nitzschia* sp. cell counts.

Materials and Methods

Data acquisition

SPATT ring construction and extraction is detailed in Lane *et al.* (2010). Three different SPATT resins are included for comparison of adsorption performance. Environmental

and toxin data was downloaded from CalHABMAP - Santa Cruz Wharf HAB repository (ERDDAP, 2022). Methods for discrete water sampling and analysis are provided in Schulien *et al.* (2017).

Statistics and analysis

Monitoring data included 13 variables with weekly sampling resolution starting the week of December 25th, 2009. SPATT rings were deployed approximately 1 m below mean lower low water level at the Santa Cruz Wharf for two to 29 days with a median and mode of 7 days. SPATT samplers were attached to a weighted rope. Toxin observations were paired with the middle date of each deployment to align multiple variables. A Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test was used to compare the shape of each SPATT timeseries and Spearman's R was used in correlation analyses (R Core Team, 2017).

For comparing multiple variables, time series were linearly interpolated across missing sample dates using weekly mean values, which resulted in a final dataset of 533 consecutive observations. The data were normalized so that each of the 13 variables had mean 0 and variance 1 prior to principal component analysis (PCA) with the factoextra package (Kassambara and Mundt, 2020). The first four principal components were retained as significant based on evaluating the scree plot for eigenvalues greater than one.

Results and Discussion

Domoic acid in SCW sentinel mussels surpassed the regulatory threshold of 20 ppm on at least one occasion annually in five out of 10 years included in the study period. Years 2014 and 2015 had notably high concentrations of

domoic acid resulting from a northeast Pacific warm anomaly (Ryan *et al.*, 2017) during a prolonged oceanic warm anomaly. Caused by diatoms of the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia*, this HAB produced the highest particulate concentrations of the biotoxin domoic acid (DA). Domoic acid spikes in sentinel mussels generally correspond to increases in all other toxin variables (Fig. 1). Two exceptions stand out. First, dissolved domoic acid in 2012 and 2020 did not increase in concert with other variables. Second, observations from SPATT in recent years show relatively high adsorbed domoic acid levels compared to other variables.

Different SPATT resins have different adsorption and extraction efficiencies (Kudela, 2017). In this dataset, domoic acid values from resins HP-20, SP-207, SP-700 were well correlated and statistically different by pairwise Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests (Table 1). Deploying multiple resins can capture different modes of dissolved toxin in the environment. For example, HP-20 has a high percent recovery and is best used to determine background domoic acid over long deployment times. In contrast, resins SP-207 and SP-700 have lower percent recovery, but respond more quickly to episodic toxin events and detect higher concentrations of domoic acid (Kudela, 2017).

The 2014-2015 bloom exhibits this pattern with SP-207 and SP-700 showing higher DA levels than HP-20 (Fig. 1). Overall, resins HP-20 and SP-700 had the best agreement, and resin SP-207 had the best correlation to non-SPATT variables including direct analysis of seawater, sentinel mussels, and cell counts. All three resins were auto-correlated over approximately two months. Resins SP-700

and HP-20 also showed an annual cycle with autocorrelation increasing approximately 52, 104, and 156 weeks after the first sample date.

Fig. 1. Ten-year time series of domoic acid variables measured approximately weekly from the Santa Cruz Wharf. (Top) SPATT resin indicated by color. Cell counts for *Pseudo-nitzschia* sp. were unavailable from March, 2016 to May, 2017.

Table 1. Summary statistics for comparing SPATT resins. Spearman's R used for correlation coefficients.

Resin pair	K-S test p-value	Spearman R ($p < 0.05$)
HP-20/SP-700	0.0010	0.75
HP-20/SP-207	0.0003	0.58
SP-207/SP-700	0.0117	0.69

The variability of domoic acid from different sampling methods was explored in broader context by principal component

analysis of 13 variables (Fig. 2). The first two dimensions explain about 41.2% of the variance, and three main clusters emerge 1) SPATT resins and temperature, 2) other toxin variables (*Pseudo-nitzschia* sp. cell counts, dissolved and particulate DA, and DA from sentinel mussels), and 3) nutrient variables (nitrate, phosphate, silicate, and ammonium). In this model, domoic acid from SPATT is not correlated to domoic acid measured by other methods. Resin SP-207 is offset from the close correlation of HP-20 and SP-700 towards the other toxin variables, indicating that results from SP-207 more closely follow direct sampling methods. Negative correlation with nutrient concentrations likely drives the relationship across dimension 1 (Dim 1).

This relationship is also apparent comparing the first and third dimensions. Including dimension 3 explains an additional 16.9% of variance, and SPATT clusters more closely with the other toxin variables. Dimension 2 is most likely influenced by changes over time. Temperature and DA from SPATT show a significant increase over 10 years ($p \ll 0.05$), while domoic acid from direct measurements, cell counts and sentinel mussels peaked mid-decade. Dimension 3 has a negative correlation to temperature, and dimension 4 is strongly influenced by ammonium and chlorophyll. Ammonium and chlorophyll only make a small contribution to the first three dimensions.

SPATT observations of domoic acid at SCW did not show clear links with other HAB and environmental variables over the 10 years. Time series analysis and PCA suggest that SPATT may be more sensitive at detecting dissolved DA than direct measurements, especially in recent years that show

Variable	Dim 1	Dim 2	Dim 3	Dim 4
Ammonium	-0.261	-0.003	0.194	0.771
Silicate	-0.469	-0.089	0.405	-0.255
Phosphate	-0.637	0.037	0.539	-0.008
Nitrate	-0.665	0.178	0.585	0.011
dDA	0.363	0.486	0.172	0.266
pDA	0.398	0.580	0.175	-0.103
musDA	0.448	0.633	0.291	0.010
<i>P. nitzschia</i>	0.460	0.705	0.301	-0.075
SP207	0.599	-0.291	0.506	0.095
SP700	0.480	-0.601	0.535	0.043
HP20	0.485	-0.626	0.534	0.033
Temp	0.466	-0.257	-0.543	0.231
Chl	0.220	-0.137	0.030	-0.653

Fig. 2. (Top) Principal component loading plot of 13 variables measured weekly at SCW. Quality of representation (Cos^2) by each dimension denoted by color and arrow length. (Bottom) Coordinates for first four dimensions.

increasing domoic acid from SPATT. The high sensitivity of SPATT and tendency towards ‘false positive’ results for toxic shellfish has been discussed in other studies as well (Fux *et al.*, 2009; Lane *et al.*, 2010; Pizarro *et al.*, 2013) a neurotoxin produced by some species of the diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia*, can remain undetected in sentinel shellfish stocks during toxic blooms and subsequent marine bird and mammal mass mortality events. Solid Phase Adsorption Toxin Tracking (SPATT. As a passive sampling device, SPATT is

analogous to an average value for dissolved toxin over the last three to seven days. Direct measurements of DA and cell counts are point samples. The offset in sampling timescale could be responsible for differences between the two variable clusters. In addition, SPATT works to concentrate dissolved DA from large volumes of water, which likely contributes to its increased sensitivity relative to point samples. The semi-quantitative nature of SPATT is another challenge in comparing passive samplers and direct measurements, since toxins extracted from SPATT are tied to resin mass and not the true dissolved concentration (Kudela, 2011). Although we were not able to elucidate environmental drivers of SPATT domoic acid in this dataset, results suggest ambient domoic acid levels in Monterey Bay are higher than expected based on direct analysis alone. For this reason, SPATT appears to be a valuable component of biotoxin monitoring, detecting toxins that evade direct sampling methods either through sensitivity and/or time-scale effects.

While there is strong evidence that consuming low-levels of domoic acid has detrimental health effects for marine mammals, birds, and humans, understanding of the effects from chronic exposure to dissolved domoic acid is less developed (Work *et al.*, 1993; Moriarty *et al.*, 2021; Petroff *et al.*, 2021) the causative agent for the human syndrome Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP. The function of SPATT as an environmental indicator has benefits over direct sampling methods for evaluating ecosystem impacts of dissolved toxins. Results from Bargu *et al.* (2006) showed that dissolved domoic acid significantly reduced the ingestion rate of krill feeding on nontoxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. in lab trials. The study used dissolved

DA concentrations up to 1,000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, much higher than measured environmental levels at the time but within range of values seen during HAB events from 2014 to 2018. Future work that focuses on the ecosystem effects of persistent dissolved toxins may help advance the impact of SPATT for applied biotoxin monitoring. Finally, this study shows the importance of rigorous, quantitative assessment of domoic acid in Monterey Bay and supports implementation of innovative monitoring methods.

Acknowledgements. Funding was provided by the NOAA Monitoring and Event Response for Harmful Algal Blooms (MERHAB) Award NA04NOS4780239 (Cal-PreEMPT), NOAA Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (ECOHAB Grant No. NA11NOS4780030), and NOAA IOOS Award NA16NOS0120021 to the Central and Northern California Ocean Observing System (CeNCOOS). Support for ICHA 2021 registration fees was generously provided by NOAA National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science (NCCOS). We would also like to give special recognition to members of the Kudela Lab for sampling work and helpful feedback throughout the project.

References

Bargu, S., Lefebvre, K., Silver, M. W. (2006). *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 312, 169-175.

ERDDAP (2022). Dataset ID: HABs-SantaCruzWharf. [//erddap.sccoos.org/erddap/tabledap/HABs-SantaCruzWharf.html](https://erddap.sccoos.org/erddap/tabledap/HABs-SantaCruzWharf.html)

Fux, E., Bire, R., Hess, P. (2009). *Harmful Algae* 8, 523-537.

Kassambara, A. and Mund, F. (2020). *factoextra: Extract and Visualize the Results of Multivariate Data Analysis*. [//www.sthda.com/english/rpkgs/factoextra](http://www.sthda.com/english/rpkgs/factoextra)

Kudela, R. M. (2011). *Harmful Algae* 11, 117-125.

Kudela, R. M. (2017). *Compr. Anal. Chem.* 78, 379-404.

Lane, J.Q., Roddam, C.M., Langlois, G.W., Kudela, R.M. (2010). *Limnol. Oceanogr. Meth.* 8, 645-660.

MacKenzie, L. A. (2010). *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 21, 326–331.

MacKenzie, L., Beuzenberg, V., Holland, P., McNabb, P., Selwood, A. (2004). *Toxicon* 44, 901-918.

Moriarty, M. E., Tinker, M. T., Miller, M. A., Tomoleoni, J. A., *et al.*, (2021). *Harmful Algae* 102, 101973.

Petroff, R., Hendrix, A., Shum, S., Grant, K. S., *et al.*, (2021). *Pharmacol. Ther.* 227, 107865.

Pizarro, G., Moroño, Á., Paz, B., Franco, J. M., *et al.*, (2013). *Mar. Drugs* 11, 3823-3845.

R Core Team (2017). [//www.R-project.org/](http://www.R-project.org/).

Roué, M., Darius, H. T., Chinain, M. (2018). *Toxins* 10, 1-28.

Ryan, J. P., Kudela, R. M., Birch, J. M., Blum, M., *et al.*, (2017). *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 44, 5571-5579.

Schulien, J. A., Peacock, M. B., Hayashi, K.,

Raimondi, P., Kudela, R. M. (2017). Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser. 572, 43-56.

Work, T. M., Barr, B., Beale, A. M., Fritz, L., *et al.*, (1993). J. Zoo Wildl. Med. 24, 54-62.

